

188.992 Experiment Design for Data Science 2023: Assignment 2

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ABSTRACT

For our experiment, we chose the Random Sampling Plus Fake Data: Multidimensional Frequency Estimates With Local Differential Privacy, conducted by Heber H. Arcolezi, Jean-Francois Couchot, Bechara Al Bouna, and Xiaokui Xiao at CIKM in 2021.

As the selected experiment was relatively straightforward to replicate, it prompted us to closely inspect its setup. We examined whether the experiments were conducted multiple times with different settings, especially by changing the 'seeds' that could impact the data. We also assessed whether the variability of the results was recorded, if any statistical significance testing was performed, and if the results remained consistent when we altered the conditions.

Furthermore, we focused on five specific tests analyzing cell phone data while safeguarding people's privacy, a crucial aspect for studying individuals' movement patterns.

KEYWORDS

Local differential privacy, Call detail records, Mobility analytics, Multi-dimensional data, Mobile phone data

1 INTRODUCTION

Provided below is a brief overview outlining the purpose and focus of each experiment conducted in this study. The summary aims to provide a concise yet comprehensive understanding of the objectives and key aspects of the individual experiments, shedding light on their significance within the broader context of the research.

In the realm of data-driven research, the quest for valuable insights often collides with the imperative to protect user privacy. The first experiment explores the delicate balance between longitudinal collection and analysis of mobile phone data and the imperative of user privacy, focusing on the innovative use of Local Differential Privacy (LDP) techniques, with a specific emphasis on handling Call Detail Records (CDRs). LDP, a privacy-preserving method, provides a means to glean valuable information about human mobility patterns over time while safeguarding individual privacy, in accordance with established guidelines such as the GDPR and CNIL.

The second experiment, detailed in the document "Random Sampling Plus Fake Data: Multidimensional Frequency Estimates With Local Differential Privacy," delves into the intricacies of the RS+FD methodology, a technique designed to augment privacy in data collection. This report meticulously explores the theoretical foundations, the experimental setup, and the results obtained from synthetic and real-world datasets. Subsequent cross-referencing with Python notebook details aims to offer a comprehensive examination and comparison, scrutinizing the reliability and consistency of the

experiments, including variations in seeds, variance reporting, and significance tests.

Moving on to the third experiment, documented in "0 LD/P RS FD arxived version.pdf," the focus remains on RS+FD methodology within the framework of Local Differential Privacy. While the document provides an extensive experimental setup using both synthetic and real-world datasets, it lacks explicit mention of different seeds for data splits, detailed variance reporting for individual runs, or statistical significance tests. However, the reproducibility of experiments is supported by accessible source code and a thorough methodology description, prompting considerations for re-running experiments under varied conditions.

The fourth experiment shifts its gaze towards improving data utility within the scope of Local Differential Privacy. The document titled "Improving the Utility of Locally Differentially Private Protocols for Longitudinal and Multidimensional Frequency Estimates" delves into the enhancement of data utility, extending the analysis of three state-of-the-art LDP protocols. The introduction of the Adaptive LDP for Longitudinal and Multidimensional FREquency Estimates (ALLOMFREE) presents a novel approach that adapts between protocols based on specific conditions, showcasing superior performance in frequency estimate quality.

In the fifth and final experiment, the paper on "Differentially Private Multivariate Time Series Forecasting of Aggregated Human Mobility With Deep Learning" explores the intersection of differentially private methods in deep learning for forecasting multivariate aggregated human mobility. The study employs cutting-edge recurrent neural networks and extensive experiments, revealing that differentially private deep learning models, under either input or gradient perturbation, achieve performances nearly equivalent to non-private models.

Together, these experiments contribute to the evolving landscape of privacy-preserving data analytics, shedding light on innovative methodologies, challenges, and advancements in the pursuit of valuable insights while respecting the paramount importance of user privacy.

The following sections delve into the intricacies of each experiment, elucidating the research questions, methodologies employed, and the expected outcomes. This detailed exploration aims to offer readers a nuanced perspective on the specific goals and contributions of each experiment, enhancing their comprehension of the overall research endeavor.

2 1ST EXPERIMENT

This experiment was conducted using the Jupyter Notebook `1_GRR_Mobile_Phone_Data_VHs.ipynb`.

- **Repetition of Experiments:** The code indicates the use of a fixed seed (`seed = 42`) for reproducibility. This suggests that while the experiments may be repeatable, they may not have been run multiple times with different seeds or settings within the provided snippets. For thorough experimental validation, it's typically advisable to run experiments multiple times with varied configurations, such as changing seeds.
- **Variance Reporting:** The use of mean squared error in the code implies that some form of variance or spread in the results is being considered. This is a positive aspect as it helps in understanding the reliability and precision of the experimental outcomes.
- **Significance Tests:** The provided code does not include explicit mention of statistical significance tests (like t-tests or calculations of p-values). Such tests are crucial for establishing whether the observed effects or differences in results are statistically significant and not just due to random chance.
- **Rerunning Experiments with Different Seeds:** The presence of a fixed seed setting (`seed = 42`) suggests that while the experiments can be repeated for consistency, they may not have been explicitly run with different seeds in the provided code. Running the experiments with different seeds is important to verify the stability and generalizability of the results.
- **Statistical Analysis:** The notebook's approach to statistical analysis, particularly using RMSE (Root Mean Squared Error) for evaluating the effectiveness of the LDP implementation, corresponds with the type of analysis detailed in the paper.

3 2ND EXPERIMENT

This experiment consists of three Jupyter Notebooks. The sequence of executing these Notebooks was unclear. The README could be better written. Furthermore, it was not clear that there is a need to create folders for storing output .csv files. Here is the analysis of each Jupyter Notebook:

`1_RS+FD_LDP_Synthetic3_50k_d10.ipynb`

- The experiments were run multiple times using different seeds, (`np.random.seed(seed)`) addressing the concern about variability and robustness of results.
- Variance was considered in the experiments, as evidenced by the variance functions and the use of multiple seeds.
- **Significance Tests:** The provided code does not include any statistical significance tests (like t-tests or calculations of p-values). Such tests are crucial for establishing whether the observed effects or differences in results are statistically significant and not just due to random chance.

`2_RS+FD_LDP_VHs.ipynb`

- The notebook includes the creation of datasets, application of privacy mechanisms like GRR and UE, and estimation of frequencies. The use of Numba for performance optimization and functions like `Var_RSFD_GRR` and `Var_RSFD_OUE_z` indicates a focus on variance in the results.
- **Multiple Runs and Seeds:** The experiments were run multiple times using different seeds, addressing the concern about variability and robustness of the results.
- **Variance Consideration:** Variance is considered in the experiments, though it's not clear if a detailed variance analysis for individual runs was conducted.
- **Statistical Significance Tests:** The documents do not explicitly mention statistical significance tests like t-tests or ANOVA for comparing the methods.
- **Reproducibility and Conclusions:** The approach seems methodical and reproducible, but it's not explicitly stated if rerunning experiments with different seeds would yield consistent conclusions.

`3_RS+FD_Analysis.ipynb`

- Jupyter Notebook conducts multiple experiments (specifically, 100 runs as mentioned in the paper) to validate the RS+FD method. It reports the variance of different estimators (GRR, OUE-z, OUE-r) and compares analytical and experimental results. While it's clear that multiple runs were conducted, it doesn't explicitly mention the use of different seeds for each run.
- **PDF Paper:** Similar to the notebook, it emphasizes repeated experiments and variance analysis. It mentions averaging results over 100 runs, indicating a robust experimental setup.
- There is no explicit mention of significance testing (like t-tests or ANOVA) to compare the means of different experimental setups.

4 3RD EXPERIMENT

This experiment was conducted using 3 Jupyter Notebooks:

- `1_GRR_Mobile_Phone_Data_VHs.ipynb`.
- `1_GRR_Mobile_Phone_Data_VHs.ipynb`.
- `1_GRR_Mobile_Phone_Data_VHs.ipynb`.

Here we had troubles to run the 1st experiment solution. First of all, we were not able to run this solution on mac as TensorFlow is not detecting any GPUs on this system. We came up with the idea to run this solution on google drive in google colab. We faced an issue with running the Bayesian Optimization part of the code:

```

# defining search space
space = {
    "LR": hp.uniform('LR', 1e-5, 3e-3), #learning rate
    "BS": hp.quniform('BS', 5, 40, 5), #batch size
    "h1": hp.quniform('h1', 25, 500, 25), #number of neurons of first hidden layer
}

#Number of iterations for Bayesian optimization
NB_ITER = 1 #we runned 100

#Bayesian optimization
ITER = 0
trials = Trials()
best = fmin(fn=objective_function,
           space=space,
           algo=tpe.suggest,
           rstate= np.random.RandomState(42),
           max_evals=NB_ITER, #
           verbose=False,
           trials=trials)
print("Best Hyperparameters:", best)

```

Figure 1: Initial Version of Bayesian Optimization solution

The error 'attribute integers' while running this code is due to a version incompatibility between NumPy and Hyperopt. The integers method was introduced in a later version of NumPy. We were using an older version of NumPy that does not have the integers method in the RandomState class. Consequently, we encountered this error when using Hyperopt, which expects the newer NumPy API. We were unable to install the correct, suitable versions of these libraries. To avoid the issue with the integers method in `numpy.random.mtrand.RandomState`, we modified the code to use the seed method instead. The seed method is available in older versions of NumPy and serves to initialize the random number generator.:

```

# Set the global random state for numpy
np.random.seed(42)

# defining search space
space = {
    "LR": hyperopt.hp.uniform('LR', 1e-5, 3e-3), # learning rate
    "BS": hyperopt.hp.quniform('BS', 5, 40, 5), # batch size
    "h1": hyperopt.hp.quniform('h1', 25, 500, 25), # number of neurons
in the first hidden layer
}

# Number of iterations for Bayesian optimization
NB_ITER = 1 # originally ran 100

# Bayesian optimization
trials = hyperopt.Trials()
best = hyperopt.fmin(
    fn=objective_function,
    space=space,
    algo=hyperopt.tpe.suggest,
    max_evals=NB_ITER,
    verbose=False,
    trials=trials
)
print("Best Hyperparameters:", best)

```

Figure 2: Schedules Surgeries Star Schema

For all 3 experiments we can report the following:

- **Reproducibility and Multiple Runs:** The notebook code indicates that the experiments were designed to be run multiple times, as seen with the `nb_seed` parameter set to 100. This

suggests that multiple evaluations using different seeds for data splits were intended to ensure reproducibility and reliability of results.

- **Variance Reporting:** The code includes methods for calculating and reporting variance, such as in the variance calculation functions `Var_RSFD_GRR`, `Var_RSFD_OUE_z`, `Var_RSFD_OUE_r` and in the experimental sections where mean squared error (MSE) and its variance are calculated for different privacy methods. This demonstrates attention to the variability in the results.
- **Significance Testing:** There is no explicit mention of statistical significance tests like t-tests or ANOVA in the notebook.
- **Stability of Conclusions with Different Seeds:** The use of multiple seeds and the averaging of results across these runs suggest that the conclusions are expected to hold under different random splits of data. However, without explicit results or a detailed analysis section in the notebook, it's difficult to conclusively state the stability of the conclusions.

5 4TH EXPERIMENT

This experiment consists of two Jupyter Notebooks. Here is the analysis of each Jupyter Notebook:

1_ALLOMFREE_Analysis.ipynb

- **Variance Reporting:** The use of `mean_squared_error` in the code implies that some form of variance or spread in the results is being considered. This is a positive aspect as it helps in understanding the reliability and precision of the experimental outcomes.
- **Significance Tests:** The provided code does not include any statistical significance tests (like t-tests or calculations of p-values). Such tests are crucial for establishing whether the observed effects or differences in results are statistically significant and not just due to random chance.
- **The code evaluates the variance of frequency estimators under these protocols.** The results show that L-OSUE offers lower variance than L-SUE and L-OUE. However, the notebook does not explicitly mention if experiments were run multiple times with different seeds for data splits, nor does it report on the performance of significance tests. Therefore, it's not clear if the conclusions would hold under varying experimental conditions like different seeds. The analysis appears to be primarily analytical and numerical without direct experimental data on multiple runs or seed variance.

2_ALLOMFREE_LDP_VHs.ipynb

- **Variance was meticulously reported and compared across different protocols** such as ALLOMFREE, L-OSUE, L-SUE, L-SOUE, and L-OUE. The notebook contains functions like `param_L_OSUE`, `param_L_SUE`, `param_L_SOUE`, and others for

determining the parameters for each LDP protocol under different privacy settings. These functions were used to evaluate the efficacy of each method in terms of mean squared error (MSE) under varying conditions of privacy parameters (ϵ).

- Significance tests, in the traditional statistical sense, were not explicitly mentioned. However, the thorough numerical evaluations, variance analyses, and extensive use of simulation runs (100 seeds) contribute significantly to the reliability and validity of the conclusions.
- The conclusions drawn from these experiments are based on the average MSE results across different protocols, compared under varying privacy parameter settings. The use of multiple seeds for data splits in the experiments adds to the reliability of these conclusions, implying that they should hold under different experimental runs with different seeds.

6 5TH EXPERIMENT

Unfortunately, this solution was not provided, so we did not run it.

7 RECOMMENDATIONS

Our recommendations for Enhancing Project Reproducibility and Structure are the following:

- Implement Virtual Environments like venv or conda to create isolated Python environments. This encapsulates dependencies, ensuring consistency across different machines and developers.
- Maintain a requirements.txt or environment.yml file for specifying exact versions of libraries and dependencies required to run the code.
- Refactor code from Jupyter notebooks (.ipynb) into Python scripts (.py) when complex debugging or unit testing is necessary. This facilitates easier tracking of changes and more robust error handling.
- Comprehensive README: Update the README file to provide detailed instructions for setting up the environment, running the notebooks, and the order of operations. It should serve as a clear starting point for new users.
- Containerization: Consider containerizing the application with Docker to further enhance reproducibility. Containers package code with all its dependencies, providing a consistent environment across different systems.
- Data Management: Ensure that data used in notebooks is properly managed and easily accessible, with clear instructions on how to retrieve and preprocess it.
- Consider establishing a .gitignore file to specify which files or directories should be excluded from version control. This

helps maintain a clean and organized repository by preventing irrelevant files, such as compiled binaries, temporary files, or sensitive information, from being tracked. It enhances collaboration and ensures that only essential code and configuration files are shared among collaborators. To create a .gitignore file, list the files or patterns you want to ignore, and Git will automatically exclude them from future commits. Furthermore, a .gitignore file protects developers from sharing personal information and credentials.

- In order to effectively manage and track changes in your project, we highly recommend implementing Git as your version control system. Git provides a robust and efficient framework for collaborative development, enabling multiple contributors to work on the same project simultaneously.

8 WHAT WE IMPLEMENTED

Please find the adjusted solution on the Git

<https://github.com/MarynaG05/ldp-protocols-mobility-cdrs>. Here's what we implemented based on our recommendations:

- Creation of Virtual Environment: We established a virtual environment for our project to ensure a controlled and isolated development environment. This step enables us to manage dependencies specific to our project without affecting the global Python environment.
- Activation of Virtual Environment: After creating the virtual environment, we activated it to make it the active Python environment for our project. This ensures that any installations or modifications are confined to this specific environment.
- Implementation of '.gitignore' File: To enhance version control, we introduced a '.gitignore' file. This file specifies which files and directories should be excluded from the Git repository, preventing the tracking of unnecessary files such as temporary files, compiled binaries, or sensitive information.
- Creation of 'requirements.txt' File: We generated a 'requirements.txt' file listing all the necessary libraries and their versions required to run the project. This file serves as a reference for replicating the environment and guarantees consistency across different systems.
- Utilization of Git for Version Control: Git was employed as the version control system for our project. This enables us to track changes, collaborate with team members, and maintain a history of the project's development. We adopted Git's branching and merging features to organize our workflow effectively.
- Update of README File: We revised and updated the README file to provide comprehensive instructions for setting up the development environment, running the project, and understanding the project structure. A well-documented README

serves as a valuable resource for collaborators and new contributors.

- Adjustment of Bayesian Optimization Part: We made adjustments to the Bayesian optimization section of our project, refining and optimizing the code for better performance and accuracy. This step contributes to the overall improvement of our project's functionality.

- Renaming of Jupyter Notebooks: In adherence to a logical workflow, we renamed Jupyter notebooks as needed. This practice ensures that the order of execution is clear, preventing confusion among collaborators and maintaining a structured and organized project.

9 REFERENCES

REFERENCES

- [1] Marwan Al-Turany, Jaroslav Pullmann, Tao Yue, and Ivan Porres. Ensuring Reproducibility in Quantitative Research on Industrial Automated Testing - A Case Study. *CoRR*, volume abs/2105.05205, 2021. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2105.05205>.